

parboiled by the double steaming method used in conventional rice mills and dried to 14% and the other half was raw milled. Both samples were dehulled in a laboratory model Satake rubber roll huller and milled for 30 s in a McGill miller. Milling characters were estimated (see table).

All the cultivars had decreasing mean values for brown rice percentage in parboiled rice compared with raw rice because of soaking losses. Brown rice percentage in raw rice ranged from 75.4% for Improved White Ponni to 79.5% for ADT36; in parboiled rice, it ranged from 74.5% for Improved White Ponni to 77.8% for ADT39. Quantity of hull removed in parboiled rice was less than that for raw rice. The hull percentage was 20.0-23.0% in raw rice and 19.0-21.8% in parboiled rice. The most hull (23.0%) was removed from Co 45 and Improved White Ponni in raw rice and

21.8% from Improved White Ponni in parboiled rice.

Parboiling improved the milling characters in all varieties. Milling recovery ranged from 71.3% for Improved White Ponni to 75.7% for ADT39 in raw rice compared with 72.7% for Improved White Ponni to 75.9% for ADT36 in parboiled rice. The physico-chemical structure of the kernel was altered in parboiling, conferring strength to the grains due to gelatinization by double steaming and subsequent drying.

More bran was obtained with raw milling than with parboiling, with 1.1% in ADT38 and ADT39 and 4.2% in ASD18. This suggests that uniform milling for 30 s for both raw and parboiled rice is inadequate. Time should vary for uniform polishing. In raw milling, ASD18, IR64, IR50, and ASD16 yielded 5.0-5.7% bran and IR36 yielded only 3.3%, indicating that cultivars vary

in hardness and resistance of milling. On the contrary, in parboiled rice, bran yield was highest in Co 43 (3.4%) and least in ADT37(1.4%), perhaps because of increased variation in gelatinization for the cultivars, even under similar conditions (see table).

Head rice recovery in parboiled rice was much greater than that in raw rice. The head rice recovery of the cultivars under the raw rice treatment was relatively lower than their normal averages because of the environmental conditions to which samples were exposed from harvest until analysis. Cultivars, however, may respond differently to head rice recovery because of genetics.

In both raw and parboiled rices, no definite trend was observed in brown rice, total milled rice, head rice, and hull and bran content, suggesting that genetics and the environment largely govern the characters. ■

Milling characters (%) for raw and parboiled rice of 15 popular cultivars. TNRRRI, Aduthurai, India. 1992.

Variety	Raw rice					Parboiled rice				
	Brown rice	Hull	Total milled rice	Bran	Head rice	Brown rice	Hull	Total milled rice	Bran	Head rice
IR50	77.7	21.9	72.7	5.0	50.0	76.4	20.5	74.0	2.4	71.0
TKM9	78.1	20.9	73.2	4.6	48.5	76.5	20.4	73.7	2.8	72.8
ADT37	79.0	20.5	75.1	3.9	53.5	77.3	19.4	75.6	1.4	74.5
Co 37	78.4	20.6	74.1	4.0	41.1	77.0	19.2	75.4	1.5	74.6
ADT36	79.5	20.0	74.9	4.5	46.8	77.6	19.0	75.9	1.5	73.8
IR36	79.2	20.2	75.2	3.3	52.5	77.3	19.7	75.3	2.0	74.0
IR64	77.7	22.0	72.4	5.2	46.7	77.0	21.0	73.9	2.8	71.7
ASD16	78.6	21.0	72.8	5.0	45.0	75.9	19.8	74.1	1.8	73.1
ASD18	78.5	20.6	72.6	5.7	46.9	76.9	20.1	75.3	1.6	74.0
ADT39	79.7	20.0	75.7	3.9	51.6	77.8	19.5	75.8	2.8	73.9
IR20	78.2	21.2	73.2	4.8	46.5	76.9	19.5	74.5	2.6	72.8
ADT38	78.4	21.5	74.4	3.9	52.2	77.4	20.5	74.4	2.8	72.8
Co 43	78.0	21.7	73.0	4.8	54.9	76.6	20.2	73.0	3.4	71.5
Co 45	76.5	23.0	71.6	4.7	40.8	76.5	20.7	73.8	2.7	72.2
Improved White Ponni	75.4	23.0	71.3	3.9	47.4	74.5	21.8	72.7	1.8	71.3
\bar{X}	78.2	21.2	73.5	4.5	48.3	76.8	20.1	74.4	2.7	72.9
SD	1.1	0.9	1.30	0.62	4.06	0.78	0.73	0.93	0.61	1.15

Induction of mutants with low amylose content in endosperm using a chemical mutagen, N-methyl-N-nitrosourea

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With the increasing demand for quality rice in China, we are focusing on breeding cultivars with good eating quality.

According to our recent surveys, urban people in Yunnan Province prefer soft-cooked rice with low amylose content. We studied how changes in the environment affect amylose content in the endosperm. An improved japonica cultivar, Hexi 4, was grown in Yunnan Province at five locations with different

altitudes (Table 1). Temperature during grain-filling markedly affected amylose content, with temperature below 20 °C enhancing it. Based on this finding, we are selecting elite breeding lines with lower amylose under low temperatures for high-altitude regions.

There are some traditional and improved indica cultivars with low amylose grains that are soft-cooking in Yunnan Province. We do not, however, have such japonica germplasm in the

Table 1. Amylose content in endosperm of Hexi 4, grown at 5 locations with different altitudes in Yunnan Province, China.

Location	Altitude (m)	Average daily temperature in July (°C)	Amylose content (%)
Shunghshao	2140	18.6	19.8
Kunming	1916	19.8	18.9
Yuxi	1637	20.9	16.4
Yiliang	1550	21.7	16.4
Huanian	1000	24.3	15.4

Table 2. Amylose content in endosperm of mutant lines induced by N-methyl-N-nitrosourea treatment in Hexi 4.

Mutant or cultivar	Origin	Amylose content (%)
Hexi 4	Yunnan	20.1
94YM01 (dull)	Mutant	11.3
94YM02 (waxy)	Mutant	1.0
Koshihikari ^a	Japan	16.5
Nipponbare ^b	Japan	21.5

^aMost popular variety in Japan, has good eating quality.

^bUsed as standard for eating quality tests in Japan.

YAAS Crop Germplasm Institute. So we tried to induce low-amylose mutants by treating the fertilized eggs of a nonwaxy cultivar, Hexi 4, with N-methyl-N-nitrosourea (Table 2). We obtained two mutants, one of which was waxy and the other with very low amylose or dull endosperm. The mutant lines and Hexi 4 only differed slightly in heading time, plant height, and plant type. These lines are useful for improving the quality of japonica rice cultivated in the high altitudes of the subtropics and tropics. ■

Gan Wan Xian 19: high-yielding indica rice variety with improved grain quality

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The Jiang Xi Provincial Seedboard released Gan Wan Xian 19 in 1992. It is a new semidwarf indica rice variety derived from the cross between Hei Shi Tou, a traditional variety, and F4084, a strain from the cross IR2061/Ai Gan Nuo/Ru Wei Tao. It is suitable for late sowing in the double-cropped area of southern China.

Gan Wan Xian 19 is 95-102 cm in height and has strong stems. It matures in 134 d and has high yield potential under good irrigation and management conditions. In regional trials, the average yield was 6.8 t/ha, 11.6% more than that of M112, a local check in southern China. The highest yield obtained was 8.7 t/ha in the Huzhou region of central Jiangxi in 1993.

The variety possesses resistance to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. It has tolerance for water

Table 1. Reaction^a of Gan Wan Xian 19 to blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper.

Province ^{b/} institute	Leaf blast		Neck blast		Bacterial blight		Whitebacked planthopper	
	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c	Rating	Reaction ^c
Zhejiang	5	S	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Yunnan	3	MR	3	MR	-	-	-	-
Hunan	2	MR	0	HR	-	-	-	-
Guandong	5	S	0	HR	3.7	R-MR	-	-
Jilin	3	MR	-	-	-	-	-	-
Jianmu	-	-	-	-	2.9	HR-R	-	-
China National Rice Research Institute	-	-	-	-	5.7	MR-S	3	R

^aScored using a 0-9 scale for leaf blast, and a 0, 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 scale for neck blast, bacterial blight, and whitebacked planthopper. ^bData from the plant protection Institute of each province. ^cS = susceptible, MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, HR = highly resistant.

submergence in the areas where floods are frequent (Table 1).

Gan Wan Xian 19 has long, slender, translucent grains with intermediate amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and soft gel consistency. It won a silver prize for its high quality at the First China Agricultural Product Exposition in October 1992 (Table 2).

The variety was grown on 66,000 ha in Jiang Xi in 1993 and has been spreading quickly in other parts of southern China. ■

Table 2. Quality characteristics of Gan Wan Xian 19.1992.

Characteristic	Mean
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.0
Brown rice (%)	79.8
Milled rice recovery (%)	73.1
Head rice (%)	55.3
Kernel length (mm)	7.1
Length-width ratio	3.6
Chalky kernel (%)	8.0
Area with chalkiness (%)	1.7
Amylose content (%)	21.3
Alkali spreading value	7.0
Gel consistency (mm)	76.0
Protein content of brown rice (%)	8.2

Physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters of some rice cultivars in Tamil Nadu, India

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Growers, traders, millers, and consumers prefer different rice cultivars because of their grain yield and quality characters. We attempted to catalog certain physical, milling, chemical, and cooking characters in 16 rice cultivars commonly grown in Tamil Nadu, India.

Nine of these cultivars are short-duration (105-120 d), six are medium-

duration (121-140 d), and one is long-duration (more than 145 d). All are recommended for the lowland ecosystem. The short-duration cultivars were grown in 1992 dry season (Jun-Sep), and the medium- and long-duration varieties in 1992-93 wet season (Aug-Feb), following recommended practices. Grain was harvested, cleaned, and dried to 14%